

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE: MNRJ-R

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

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INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **When writing a conclusion, which of the following is NOT allowed?**
 - It should restate the author answer to the question.
 - It should introduce new information or ideas.¹**
 - It should re-summarise the main points.
 - It should include a final, broad statement (about possible implications, future directions for research, to qualify the conclusion, etc.).
2. **Which of the following is NOT considered as the reason for mentioning the source?**
 - Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
 - It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

- It is not a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.²**
- To allow your readers to check your sources, if there are questions.
3. **There is a great deal of information available on the internet as well as in the media and in the library. However, before we use this information, we need to ask ourselves questions to judge whether or not our sources are trustworthy. If we use unreliable information, the report or project will also be unreliable.³ Which of the following is NOT the right question to ask?**
- Is the source primary or secondary?
- Is the source biased?
- Is the source an expert?
- Is the information accurate?
- Is the information complete?
- Is the information current?
- Is the information contains spelling error?**
4. **Which of the following is NOT belonged to synthesizing information?**

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 5-11.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 264.

- Invent a better way of doing something.
 - Blend the old with the new.
 - Predict or hypothesize (make an educated guess).
 - Point out a subject's strengths and weaknesses.⁴**
5. **When writing the academic paper, the paper will seem to be incomplete and unconvincing unless the writers answer following questions⁵ many times except:**

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 290.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 42.

- What are you claiming?
 - What are your reasons?
 - What evidence supports your reasons?
 - But what about other points of view?
 - What principle makes your reasons relevant to your claims?
 - Which style guide to use?**
6. **The number of reliable Internet sources grows every day, but they are still islands in a swamp of misinformation. If you find data available on the Internet, look for sites or online publications with these signs of reliability. Which of the following is considered NOT reliable?**
- The site is sponsored by a reputable organization.
 - It is related to a reliable professional journal.
 - It supplements reliable print sources.
 - It avoids heated advocacy for or against a contested social issue.
 - It does not make wild claims, attack other researchers, use abusive language, or make errors of spelling, punctuation, and grammar.
 - It does not indicate when the site was last updated.⁶**
7. **Which of the following is correct way of presenting Times if to follow University of Oxford Style Guide?⁷**

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 29.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 80.

- The meeting starts at 14.00pm.
- The meeting starts at 11.30am and ends at 13:00.
- The closing date for applications is 12 noon on 12 July
- The closing date for applications is noon on 12 July.**

8. **Careful writing can help draft a perfectly good research paper. However, erroneous writing can cost a lot put all writing efforts in vain if when an editor/or reviewer rejects your paper.⁸ Which of the following is NOT considered as common errors in research paper?**

- Irrelevant information such as anecdotal information, unnecessary background, subjectivity and use of superlatives, and material that is inappropriate for the readership
- Simplification**
- Superficiality
- Anthropomorphism
- The significance of ‘significance’

9. **Em rule is NOT used⁹**

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 5-10.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. (Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 21.

- To introduce an explanation or amplification of what immediately precedes it
- To gather up the subject of a long or complicated sentence
- To introduce a paradoxical or humorous ending to a sentence
- To indicate the omission of a word
- To show ranges of any kind.**

10. **Which of the following is NOT the advantage of WHO House Style?**¹⁰

- House style ensures consistency
- House style contributes to a corporate image of “one WHO”
- House style improves peer review acceptance**
- House style streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process

¹⁰ World Health Organization, 1.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.